

DOI

MODELLING OF THE INFLUENCE OF TRANSPORT SYSTEM MODERNIZATION ON THE EFFICIENCY OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY

Olena Kryvoruchko

*Ph.D. candidate with The National University of Water and Environmental Engineering,
(Rivne, Ukraine)*

<https://orcid.org/>

e-mail: o.p. kryvoruchko@nuwm.edu.ua

Abstract. The model of dependence between the volume of capital investments and gross domestic product (GDP) by type of activity "Transport, warehousing, postal and courier activities" is determined. The following macroeconomic indicators were used as experimental data to calculate the dependence of Ukraine's GDP growth on the volume of investment in the transport sector: statistical data on capital investment and gross domestic product by type of activity "Transport, warehousing, postal and courier activities"; the amount of investment in land and pipeline transport at actual prices; volume of investments in water transport; volume of investments in air transport; volume of investments in warehousing and ancillary activities in the field of transport; volume of investments in postal and courier activities.

Comparative study of quality of iterative linear and combinatorial algorithms applying a group method of data handling (GMDH) is carried out and efficiency of use of group method of data handling at forecasting of GDP is shown. It is proved that the indicators used in GDP forecasting have a joint (synergistic) multiplier effect on GDP, which indicates a nonlinear relationship between the investment indicators used and GDP. Using a combined iterative-combinatorial (sqcombi c) model, the forecast value of GDP for the next year is determined. The forecast quarterly values of variables for the next year are determined by calculating the values of the linear trend in Excel. To forecast capital investments, the equation of linear trends of capital investments for each type of economic activity of future periods is obtained and the forecast of the total volume of capital investments is obtained. The forecast value of GDP was calculated using a combined iterative-combinatorial model (sqcombi c), and the results of the calculation allowed to predict the following dependence. An increase in capital investment provides accelerated economic development; new technologies and processes are introduced leading to an increase in the level of competitiveness of both business entities and goods and services; staff qualification increases; the process of forming a favourable investment climate in the country, for both domestic and foreign investors, accelerates; the development of effective integration processes is taking place; the processes of integration of the domestic economy into the world economy accelerate, and the advantages of international division and cooperation are employed.

Key words: national economy, transport system, modernization, gross domestic product, informative investment indicators, modelling, capital investments, transport types.

МОДЕЛЮВАННЯ ВПЛИВУ МОДЕРНІЗАЦІЇ ТРАНСПОРТНОЇ СИСТЕМИ НА РЕЗУЛЬТАТИВНІСТЬ НАЦІОНАЛЬНОЇ ЕКОНОМІКИ

Олена Криворучко

Аспірант, Національний університет водного господарства та природокористування, (Рівне, Україна)

<https://orcid.org/>

e-mail: o.p.kryvoruchko@nuwm.edu.ua

Анотація. Визначено модель залежності між обсягом капітальних інвестицій та валовим внутрішнім продуктом (ВВП) за видом діяльності «Транспорт, складське господарство, поштова та кур'єрська діяльність». В якості експериментальних даних для обчислення залежності росту ВВП України від обсягу інвестицій в транспортну галузь використано такі макроекономічні показники: статистичні дані капітальних інвестицій та валового внутрішнього продукту за видом діяльності «Транспорт, складське господарство, поштова та кур'єрська діяльність»; обсяг інвестицій в наземний і трубопровідний транспорту фактичних цінах; обсяг інвестицій в водний транспорт; обсяг інвестицій в авіаційний транспорт; обсяг інвестицій в складське господарство та допоміжну діяльність у сфері транспорту; обсяг інвестицій в поштову та кур'єрську діяльність. Проведено порівняльні дослідження якості ітераційних лінійних та комбінаторних алгоритмів методом групового урахування аргументів (МГУА). Показана ефективність використання методів групового врахування аргументів при прогнозуванні ВВП. Доведено, що використані показники при прогнозуванні мають сумісний (синергетичний) мультиплікативний вплив на ВВП, що свідчить про нелінійні взаємозв'язки між використаними інвестиційними показниками і результируючим показником розвитку економіки – ВВП. За допомогою комбінованої ітераційно-комбінаторної (sqcombi c) моделі визначено прогнозне значення ВВП на наступний рік. Визначено прогнозні квартальні значення змінних на наступний рік за допомогою розрахунку значень лінійного тренду в Excell. Для прогнозування капітальних інвестицій отримано рівняння лінійних трендів капітальних інвестицій по кожному виду економічної діяльності майбутніх періодів і отримано прогноз загального обсягу капітальних інвестицій. Прогнозне значення ВВП, розраховане з допомогою комбінованої ітераційно-комбінаторної моделі (sqcombi c), а результати розрахунку дозволили спрогнозувати таку залежність: при збільшенні обсягу капітальних інвестицій забезпечується прискорений розвиток економіки; впроваджуються нові технології та процеси, що призводять до зростання рівня конкурентоспроможності і суб'єктів господарювання, і товарів й послуг; підвищується кваліфікація персоналу; прискорюється процес формування інвестиційного клімату в країні, сприятливого і для вітчизняних, і для зарубіжних інвесторів; відбувається розвиток ефективних інтеграційних процесів, прискорюються процеси інтеграції вітчизняної економіки в світову економіку, здійснюється використання переваг міжнародного поділу і кооперації.

Ключові слова: національна економіка, транспортна система, модернізація, валовий внутрішній продукт (ВВП), інформативні інвестиційні показники, моделювання, капітальні інвестиції, види транспорту.

Target setting and its significance. Successful implementation of investment policy will contribute to the implementation of one of the main tasks of the country's economy, which is to increase the number of major sources of domestic investment resources. This will create the necessary preconditions for growth in production and expanded reproduction of GDP to improve the welfare of the population. Therefore, it is expedient to determine the informative investment indicators that particularly influence the dynamics of Ukraine's GDP.

Actual scientific researches and issues analysis. The following scientists have conducted studies to tackle the problem, inter alia on modelling the systems impact on the efficiency of the national economy by group method of data handling: A. Bulgakova, A. Horshkov, A. Ivakhnenko, V. Zosimov, V. Stepashko, Yu. Yurachkovskiyi.

Using the basic method, we are to model the relationship between the amount of capital investment and GDP by type of activity "Transport, warehousing, postal and courier activities".

The aim of the article is to model the impact of the transport system modernization on the efficiency of the national economy.

The statement of basic materials. Definition of the model of dependence between the volume of capital investments and GDP by type of activity "Transport, warehousing, postal and courier activities". The following macroeconomic indicators for the period from 2012 (1st quarter) to 2018 (4th quarter), 28 points in total, were taken as experimental data for calculating the dependence of Ukraine's GDP growth (UAH million) on the volume of investments in the transport sector (statistical data on capital investment and gross domestic product by type of activity "Transport, warehousing, postal and courier activities" are given in Table 3.13): x₁ - the amount of investment in ground and pipeline transport at actual prices; x₂ - the amount of investment in water transport; x₃ - the amount of investment in air transport; x₄ - the amount of investment in warehousing and ancillary activities in the transport sector; x₅ - the amount of investment in postal and courier activities.

In total, the sample contains 5 variables and 28 points and is divided into two parts: 16 measurements - training sample A (data for the period: 1st quarter of 2012 - 4th quarter of 2015); 12 measurements - validation sample B (data for the period: 1st quarter of 2016 - 4th quarter of 2018).

Table 1.1

Statistical data on capital investment and gross domestic product by type of activity "Transport, warehousing, postal and courier activities"*

Quarter / Years	Capital investments, UAH million					GDP, UAH million
	Ground and pipeline transport	Water transport	Air transport	Warehousing and ancillary activities in the transport sector	Postal and courier activities	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
	X ₁	X ₂	X ₃	X ₄	X ₅	Y
Q1 2012	1 992,1	35,7	275,3	2 820,1	20,4	292 324
Q2 2012	4 378,5	26,8	176,0	3 642,6	35,4	346 005
Q3 2012	2 601,8	41,7	133,5	3 581,9	168,0	387 109
Q4 2012	3 691,8	28,4	195,2	4 140,5	172,4	379 231
Q1 2013	587,8	6,3	98,6	1 779,2	5,0	303 753
Q2 2013	1 189,4	37,3	137,6	2 042,0	5,1	354 814
Q3 2013	1 440,2	31,8	131,6	3 039,0	8,2	398 000
Q4 2013	1 650,3	21,4	155,3	3 929,4	202,1	408 631
Q1 2014	590,3	29,3	73,3	1 876,8	3,8	316 905

Q2 2014	1 140,6	41,0	79,2	2 230,4	4,1	382 391
Q3 2014	652,3	89,0	71,4	1 820,4	9,1	440 476
Q4 2014	1 072,6	48,8	96,2	3 921,9	105,5	447 143
Q1 2015	1 805,6	23,1	116,3	904,4	4,9	375 991
Q2 2015	874,6	96,2	193,7	1 935,6	2,8	456 715
Q3 2015	2 386,9	111,6	125,6	2 083,2	5,3	566 997
Q4 2015	2 150,9	102,9	223,1	3 058,7	72,6	588 841
Q1 2016	1 952,2	36,6	99,2	1 439,6	13,3	455 298
Q2 2016	2 256,5	38,0	177,7	2 114,6	22,5	535 701
Q3 2016	3 365,5	53,3	218,4	2 646,5	18,7	671 456
Q4 2016	7 383,0	106,2	202,3	2 527,1	66,5	722 912
Q1 2017	3 693,0	50,8	210,2	1 454,0	6,6	592 523
Q2 2017	4 181,9	55,4	260,4	1 979,0	51,8	665 233
Q3 2017	4 627,7	56,9	372,2	2 852,1	53,7	834 287
Q4 2017	9 455,6	74,6	340,4	5 640,6	285,3	891 839
Q1 2018	4 542,9	28,1	508,6	3 013,7	83,7	705 013
Q2 2018	6 002,5	36,9	416,2	3 748,2	171,4	810 820
Q3 2018	6 402,9	75,0	328,0	3 466,8	61,3	994 850
Q4 2018	10 945,0	60,3	318,7	4 622,0	88,3	1 048 023

Reference [1]

To solve this problem, a group method of data handling (hereinafter GMDH) was applied. For the first time, the concept of a group method of data handling was presented by O.G. Ivakhnenko in 1971 (Ivakhnenko A.G., 1971. 392p.). As mentioned in (Ivakhnenko A.G., Stepashko V.S., 1985. 216p.), (Stepashko V.S., 2013. P.150-170), GMDH is a high-capacity information technology for solving problems of structural-parametric identification of models of complex objects, or modelling based on experimental data in conditions of uncertainty, as well as problems of data mining. Subsequently, the group method of data handling was known under various designations from “heuristic self-organization” (Ivakhnenko A.G., 1982. 296 p.), (Ivakhnenko A.G., 1971. 392p.), “inductive self-organization of models of complex systems” (Ivakhnenko A.G., 1970. P. 207-219) to “inductive modelling of complex systems”.

The basic principles of inductive modelling of complex systems include the already mentioned three, namely (Zosimov V.V., Bulgakova A.S., 2010. P. 112-118), (Ivakhnenko A.G., 1971. 392 p.), (Ivakhnenko A.G., Stepashko V.S., 1985. 216 p.): the principle of self-organization, the principle of external complementarity, and the principle of freedom of decision-making.

These principles formed the basis of the technology for solving the problems of inductive synthesis of models based on experimental data.

The following results of modelling the economic process were received. To build polynomial models used to forecast GDP, a software package based on the GMDH generalized iterative algorithm (Zosimov V.V., Bulgakova A.S., 2010. P. 112-118), and a software package “Fully Automated Knowledge Extraction using Group of Adaptive Models Evolution” (FAKE GAME), developed at the Czech Technical University in Prague, (URL: <http://fakegame.sourceforge.net/doku.php>) were used.

To model the dependence of Ukraine’s GDP growth (UAH million) on the volume of investment, iterative algorithms were used, including three linear algorithms and six with a quadratic function, including combined algorithms for building models:

a) Linear:

1) multi-row iterative (lin m);

2) relaxation (lin r);

- 3) combined iterative (lin c);
- b) With a quadratic function:
- 4) multi-row iterative with quadratic function (sq m);
- 5) relaxation quadratic function (sq r);
- 6) relaxation-combinatorial quadratic function (sq c);
- 7) multi-row iterative-combined (sqcombi m);
- 8) relationaliterative-combined (sqcombi r);
- 9) Combined iterative-combinatorial (sqcombi c).

The modelling results are given in Tables 2-3.

Table 2

Results of linear dependence modelling*

No	Algorithms for model construction	AR	R ²	Model
1	lin m	0,098382	0,55759	$y = 264387,04 + 2301,94 * x_2 + 249,56 * x_5 - 62,49 * x_3 + 13,58 * x_1$
2	lin r	0,109024	0,560755	$y = 376393,94 + 64,00 * x_4$
3	lin c	0,095903	0,528762	$y = 284895,56 + 2287,49 * x_2 + 346,53 * x_5 - 83,39 * x_3 - 10,18 * x_4 + 16,85x_1$

*Source: Constructed by the author

The quality of the constructed model was calculated under subsample B as the value of the regularity criterion, AR (). The accuracy of the model was also checked on subsample B as the value of the coefficient of determination R² .

Table 3

Results of quadratic dependence modelling*

No.	Algorithms for model construction	AR Norm	R ²	Model
4	sq m	0,095903	0,522869	$y = 466075,21 - 1728,12 * x_2 - 116,49 * x_4 + 19,28 * x_2^2 + 0,02 * x_4^2 + 0,8 * x_2 * x_4$
5	sq r	0,054643	0,815096	$y = 132928,72 + 12,11 * x_1 + 2243,14 * x_3 + 3543,94 * x_2 + 2,95 * x_2^2 - 39,86 * x_2 * x_3 + 4,64 * x_2^2 - 0,1 * x_2^2 + 0,17 * x_2 * x_2^2 + 0,0002 * x_1 * x_4$
6	sq c	0,034439	0,809133	$y = 352822,33 - 10,27 * x_1 - 0,003 * x_1^2 + 4,93 * x_2 * x_3 + 0,004 * x_1 * x_2 * x_3 - 0,0001 * x_2^2 * x_2^2$
7	sqcombi m	0,026342	0,844991	$y = 354266,26 - 6,01 * x_1 - 351,13 * x_3 - 0,04 * x_3 * x_5 + 0,03 * x_5^2 - 0,29 * x_3^2 - 0,002 * x_1^2 + 0,98 * x_1 * x_2 + 2,8 * x_2 * x_3 - 0,0001 * x_3^2 + 0,004 * x_1 * x_2 * x_3 + 0,000001 * x_1 * x_3 * x_5 - 0,000001 * x_1 * x_2^2 + 0,000001 * x_2 * x_3 * x_5^2 + 0,000001 * x_1 * x_2 * x_3 * x_5 - 0,000002 * x_2 * x_2^2 * x_5 - 0,000006 * x_2^2 * x_2^2 - 0,000002 * x_1^2 * x_2^2$
8	sqcombi r	0,026043	0,871419	$y = 358151,48 + 1,38 * x_1 - 0,01 * x_1^2 + 0,01 * x_1 * x_2 * x_3 - 0,000000001 * x_1^2 * x_2 * x_3 + 0,000000001 * x_1^4 - 0,000000001 * x_1^3 * x_2 * x_3$
9	sqcombi c	0,009552	0,981387	$y = 292416 + 0,256097 * x_1 * x_3 - 0,198123 * x_1 * x_5 + 0,704721 * x_2 * x_4$

*Source: Constructed by the author

For each object, a remainder can be calculated $e_i = Y_i - Y_i^\Phi$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, where \hat{Y}_i is the forecast value found using the fuzzy neural network. The remainder is helpful for studying the adequacy of the data model. This means that the requirements for the independence of the remainders for individual observations should be met, the variance should not depend on X. The results of assessing the adequacy of the obtained models using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov criterion are given in Table 4.

Table 4

Statistical indicators of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov criterion for the remainders of forecasts obtained using polynomial models*

Model	Lin m	Lin r	Lin c	Sq m	Sq r	sq c	Sqcombi m	Sqcombi r	Sqcombi m
Normal distribution parameter									
Average value	6.89	-5,31	7,61	6,96	3,69	2,07	3,48	2,13	-3,31
Standard deviation	1.17	1,62	1,28	1,95	8,9	1,28	6,66	6,01	7,23
Extreme differences									
Absolute	0.217	0,155	0,247	0,159	0,199	0,117	0,119	0,095	0,162
Positive	0.217	0,155	0,247	0,159	0,199	0,072	0,119	0,095	0,082
Negative	-0.135	-0,109	-0,175	-0,116	-0,151	-0,117	-0,072	-0,054	-0,162
Z Kolmogorov-Smirnov	1.061	0,759	1,209	0,780	0,975	0,575	0,583	0,467	0,796
Significance (2-sided)	0.210	0,612	0,108	0,578	0,297	0,896	0,886	0,981	0,551
Form of distribution	Norm	Norm	Norm						

* Source: Constructed by the author

Deviation from the normal distribution is considered significant at a value of $p < 0.05$; in this case, non-parametric tests should be used for the relevant variables. In the study in all models, the probability of error is insignificant (0.210; 0.612; 0.108; 0.578; 0.297; 0.896; 0.886; 0.981; 0.551), so in all the obtained models, the values of the variables are quite well inclined to the normal distribution.

Table 5

Statistical indicators of the Fisher criterion for the remainders of forecasts obtained using polynomial models*

Model	Fisher's F-test	Significance of F	F critical
lim m	51,36	0,0000048	2,40
lin r	55,5	3,1000642	2,40
lin c	17,39	0,000004811	2,40
sq m	51,36	7,87787080	2,40
sq r	102,79	0,025940648	2,40
sq c	6,20	0,000011887	2,40
sqcombi m	43,56	0,000011887	2,40
sqcombi r	45,44	9,46225677	2,40
sqcombi c	51,36	0,00000481143	2,40

*Source: Constructed by the author

Fig. 1. Accuracy of the received models – value R^2 (Constructed by the author)

The modelling results showed that exact models were found using multi-row iterative-combined (84.5%), relational iterative-combined (87.1%), and combined iterative-combinatorial (98.1%) algorithms.

Fig. 2. Results of modelling using a combined iterative-combinatorial algorithm (Constructed by the author)

Thus, a comparative study of quality of iterative linear and combinatorial algorithms of GMDHs carried out and efficiency of use of a group method of data handling at forecasting of GDP is shown.

It is proved that the indicators used in GDP forecasting have a joint (synergistic) multiplier effect on GDP, which points to a nonlinear relationship between the investment indicators used and GDP.

We determine the forecast value of GDP for the next year using a combined iterative-combinatorial (sqcombi c) model.

At the first stage, based on the data of Table 1, the forecast quarterly values of variables ($x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4,$ and x_5) for the next year are determined by calculating the values of the linear trend in Excel.

To do this, a row of analysed data was selected, and a graph was built, where the X-axis - time series (1, 2, 3... Q1 2012, Q2 2012, Q3 2013, etc.), the Y-axis - volumes of capital investments (respectively ground and pipeline transport, water transport, air transport, warehousing and ancillary activities in the transport sector and postal and courier activities).

We add the trend line and the trend equation to the graph (see Fig. 3-7)

Fig. 3. Linear trend of capital investments in ground and pipeline transport

Fig. 4. Linear trend of capital investments in water transport

Fig. 5. Linear trend of capital investments in air transport

Fig. 6. Linear trend of capital investments in warehousing and ancillary activities in the transport sector

Fig. 7. Linear trend of capital investments in postal and courier activities

To forecast capital investments, it is required to substitute the values of future periods in the obtained equations of linear trends of capital investments for each type of economic activity (29 - Q1 2019, 30 - Q2 2019, 31 - Q3 2019 and 32 - Q4 2019). The results of the calculations are given in Table 6.

Table 6

Calculation of the forecast value of GDP *

No. of period	Quarter	Capital investments, UAH million					Forecast value of GDP, UAH million
		Ground and pipeline transport	Water transport	Air transport	Warehousing and ancillary activities in the transport sector	Postal and courier activities	
		X ₁	X ₂	X ₃	X ₄	X ₅	
29	Q1	6 480,4	71,0	335,6	3 077,1	84,7	894 649
30	Q2	6 698,2	72,4	344,6	3 096,4	86,3	927 049
31	Q3	6 916,1	73,7	353,6	3 115,7	87,8	960 359
32	Q4	7 133,9	75,1	362,7	3 135,1	89,3	994 580

$$y = 292416 + 0.256097 * x_1 * x_3 - 0.198123 * x_1 * x_5 + 0.704721 * x_2 * x_4$$

*Source: Constructed by the author.

Thus, based on defined models of linear trends, the total volume of capital investments is forecast at UAH 41.7 billion next year, which is 7.2% less than in 2018. At the same time, the forecast value of GDP, calculated using the combined iterative-combinatorial model (sqcombi c), is UAH 3,776.6 billion (6.1% more than in 2018). The calculation results are graphically depicted in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. GDP forecast by volume of capital investments (Constructed by the author)

Conclusions. The modelling of the influence of transport system modernization on the efficiency of the national economy was carried out. The modelling results show that exact models were found using multi-row iterative-combined (84.5%), relational iterative-combined (87.1%), and combined iterative-combinatorial (98.1%) algorithms. To forecast capital investments, in the equation of linear trends of capital investments for each type of economic activity, the values of future periods (25 - Q1 2018, 26 - Q2 2018, 27 - Q3 2018, and 28 - Q4 2018) should be substituted. Based on the models of linear trends for 2018, the total amount of capital investments is forecast, and the forecast value of GDP, calculated using the combined iterative-combinatorial model (sqcombi c), is UAH 2,774,347.3 million (8% less than in 2018).

The results of the calculation allowed us to predict the following dependence: an increase in capital investment provides accelerated economic development; new technologies and processes are introduced leading to an increase in the level of competitiveness of both business entities and goods and services; staff qualification increases; the process of forming a favourable investment climate in the country, for both domestic and foreign investors, accelerates; the development of effective integration processes is taking place; the processes of integration of the domestic economy into the world economy accelerate, and the advantages of international division and cooperation are employed.

References:

1. State Statistics Service of Ukraine. Retrieved from (2019) : <http://www.ukrstat.gov.ua/> (Retrieved on 25.02.2019).
2. Ivakhnenko A.G. (1971) Sistem yevristicheskoi samoorganizatsii v tekhnicheskoi kibernetike [Systems of heuristic self-organization in engineering cybernetics]. Kyiv : Tekhnika, 1971. 392p.
3. Ivakhnenko A.G., Stepashko V.S. (1985). Pomekhoustoichivost modelirovaniia [Interference immunity of modelling] : monograph. Kyiv : Naukova dumka, 1985. 216p.
4. Stepashko V.S. (2013). Samoorganizatsiia prognoziruushchikh modele I slozhnykh protsessov I sistem [Self-organization of predictive models of complex processes and systems]. Neiroinformatika-2013 : 15th All-Russian scientific and technical conf.: lectures on neuro informatics; under ed. of Yu. V. Tyumentsev. Moscow: NRNUMEPHI, 2013. P.150-170.
5. Ivakhnenko A.G. (1982) Induktivnyi metod samoorganizatsii modelei slozhnykh sistem [Inductive method of self-organization of models of complex systems]. Kyiv : Naukova dumka, 1982. 296 p.
6. Ivakhnenko A.G. (1970) Heuristic Self-Organization in Problems of Engineering Cybernetics. Automatica. 1970. № 6. P. 207-219.
7. Zosimov V.V., Bulgakova A.S. (2010) Proektirovanie program nogomoduliadlia issle dovaniia raboty algoritmov poiskovykh sistem. Problemi Modeliuvannia [Designing a software module to study the operation of search engine algorithms. Modelling Problems]. Publication 56. Kyiv : Institute for Modelling in Energy Engineering, 2010. P. 112-118.
8. Project FAKE GAME. (2020) Computation Intelligence Group. Retrieved from: <http://fakegame.sourceforge.net/doku.php> (Retrieved on 01.03.2020).